

Impact of Yoga on Prisoners' Life

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Abstract

Maharshi Patanjali¹ in his "Yoga Sutra" defines yoga in the verse, "Yogahchittavritti nirodhah", which means yoga is the blocking of mental modifications so that the seer reidentifies with the self. Swami Vivekanand calls yoga an art, a science and a philosophy. The real meaning of yoga is to unite. It brings harmony between mind and body. Yoga is important for dynamic life. Different kinds of yoga is practiced by different age groups. As in childhood mountain pose, warrior pose, tree pose, cobra pose, bridge pose etc are common yoga. Adolescents practice padmasana, siddhasana, matsyasana, halasana, bhujangasana etc. Adults practice side warrior pose, restorative yoga etc. As prisoners also have human rights to live happy and healthy life, the inmates in prison practice Amrita Yoga and Integrated Amrita Meditation Technique (IAM). Through it they learn breathing with awareness, self analysis and emotional control. In 1994, Tihar Jail organized a historical Vipassana Meditation Camp for more than one thousand prisoners. Now Vipassana Center, Brahmkumari Ishwaraiya Vishwavidyalaya, Divya Jyoti Jagriti Sansthan like meditation groups have opened their branches in jails for imparting moral education. It has helped many prisoners in changing whole approach to life.

The present study focuses on the effect of yoga in reformation, rehabilitation and recidivism of prisoners. The discussion shows that regular practices of yoga transforms the prisoners. Their mind is converted from criminal activities and negative thoughts to positive attitude towards life.

Key words: Inmates, Reformation, Rehabilitation, Recidivism, Yoga, Prison.

Introduction

It was the initiative of India and the acceptance of 175 countries of the world that United Nations declared 21 June as International Yoga Day. Yoga is not only for physical fitness but it can prevent criminal activities in our society. It can reduce vulnerability of criminal activity. Yoga habits should be started since childhood or young age. Yoga emphasizes mental discipline and refinement of soul, body and mind through guiding emotions and intellect. Sat, rajas and tamas gunas are balanced by yoga. Yoga releases negative emotions and leads to good action.

Role of Yoga in reformation and rehabilitation of Prisoners

This is unique initiative in India to reform prisoners to make their punishment less through yoga. For the first time it was started in Maharashtra prison. For it there were guidelines and directions from State Government of Maharashtra that prisoners who pass written and physical test after learning yoga, their three months punishments will be reduced. Written examination started in Yavada and different other prisons. Yoga can balance the aggressive behavior of prisoners before their release from prison and it can make them able to join the main stream of the society. Its political aspect may be to give new dimension to international yoga day and early release of prisoners. Its legal aspect is that even Supreme Court wants that the punishment of the accused should be minimized as well as Bhartiya Nyaya Samhita and rules of Jail manual permit State Govt. for such decision.

Mrs. Kiran Bedi of Indian Police Service introduced yoga and meditation classes in Tihar Jail, Delhi; where hard core criminals, narcotics and drug offenders, mass murderers are kept. For it Mrs. Bedi was appreciated by the government as well as by the public. The prisoners themselves appreciated this effort as it boosted their morale. Indian Police Officer Mrs. Kiran Bedi transformed Tihar Jail into Tihar Ashram. Stress Management And Rehabilitation Training (SMART) program was introduced by Gurudev Sri Sri Ravi Shankar in 1999 in Tihar Jail through Sudarshan Kriya. After it many prisons in India started yoga and meditation training for convicts to sublimate their aggressive and hostile feeling in socially acceptable activities.

Yoga is a vehicle for rehabilitation from crime. It makes a person physically fit and links to mindfulness, meditation, self-awareness and emotional regulations. It has a positive effect on those whose behavior is rooted in stress or trauma. Mark Norman a postdoctoral fellow in Ontario University, Canada, specialist in sport and physical recreation in prison and youth custody facilities, says that yoga programmes develop the skills that translate into anger control capability to deal with tough situation which can be a critical time when people leave prisons and go back into the community. Yoga teachers in prison say that it benefits from being a level playing fields because most participants have never done it before. It is really a challenging way of moving their bodies.

Urban yogis² use yoga to engage and divert 9 to 18 year olds away from crime gangs and anti-social behavior in the boroughs of Lambeth and Croydon in South London. Yoga is an excellent tool for helping young people who have experienced trauma. It relaxes the heart rate, makes slow and deep breath and regains control. It makes people to rest the mind and not to think about other things.

Role of Yoga in Recidivism :

Shaked Kovalsky et al (2021)³ examined the correlation between yoga practice and recidivism among released prisoners who participated in yoga programs during their incarceration in comparison with a matched control group of those who did not participate in yoga programs over a follow up period of 5 years. This study was on those prisoners who were released from the Israeli jails. Study results indicate that yoga may impact recidivism, supported by a finding of lower recidivism rates among released prisoners who had practiced yoga during their incarceration compared with the matched control group.

The tendency of a convict to once again commit a crime after release from jail is a serious issue. Recidivism rates are found in USA 55%, in UK 72% and in Australia 44.6%. In other countries like France, Germany, Netherland, Ireland etc it is above 40%.

India has traditionally adopted rehabilitation programs for prisoners involving yoga and literacy efforts. In 2015, authorities of Tihar Jail offered certificate courses in yoga training so that prisoners can get suitable job after release from prison. In 2018, under Project Sanjeevan, which was initiated in a partnership between the prison department and Morarji Desai National Institute of Yoga, more than 1000 inmates in Delhi were trained as yoga teachers. The prison department in Bihar has signed an MoU with Art of Living to teach yoga to around 48,000 inmates in 56 prisons of Bihar State.

One research by Osmania University in Telangana suggests that yoga and education drastically reduce the chance of convicts committing criminal offences after their release. In 2010, prison officials in Madhya Pradesh had launched a scheme that granted inmates reduction in their sentences if they attended and completed a three month yoga course. The prison authorities convey that yoga not only improves prisoners' fitness but also makes them calmer, less violent and positive towards life. According to National Crime Records Bureau report of 2022, India's recidivism rate is 1.9%.⁴

The condition in the jails causes inmates to suffer from anxiety, depression, aggression etc. Yoga improves mood and decreases stress. It is found in a research that pre and post yoga effects, perceived stress and psychological symptoms were entered into linear regression analysis. Yoga class attendance, self-practice, demographic variables and baseline psychometric variable were included as regressors. Particularly who attended more yoga classes and engaged five times or more per week in self practice reported significantly greater reduction of perceived stress.

Prison Yoga Project originated in California offers yoga classes to inmates in prisons across the U.S. to reduce recidivism rate. The Prison Phoenix Project runs yoga and meditation classes in 84 prisons around the U.K. and researches show that it reduced emotional distress and improved impulse control. Liberation Prison Yoga,⁵ founded by Anneke Lucas in America, essentially brings 'trauma informed' yoga to incarcerated men and women in the hopes that it will improve the quality of their life, both behind bars, and when they are released. "Trauma informed" yoga means the teachers are trained in a way that helps them bring yoga to practitioners in the gentlest & most sensitive way possible. It resulted in the prisoners' will to stop with drugs.

Effect of Yoga in Criminal Behaviour:

In Tihar Jail, New Delhi, an active social organisation for prisoners' welfare "Prayas" reports that the prisoners who attend yoga class regularly, their behavior is different from those prisoners who are not attending such classes. Yoga attending prisoners are enhancing their talents in the cultural fields as music, art as well as in sports. Its good examples is non-adult prisoner of famous Nirbhaya Case whose art work is highlighted by media.

The prisoners also feel positive effect of yoga in their life. When they go back to their society after their prison term is over, they become good persons of the society. They usually do not repeat crimes provided the yoga and meditation genuinely benefit them. Follow up observations of convicts show that they improve their character after attending yoga and meditation classes.

Suggestions:

- Yoga classes in prisons can help inmates in decrease of their psychological distress and in improve of their behavior. It can be effective in keeping them out of prison after their release.
- Prison authorities must work with AYUSH centers to bring yoga to jail.
- All prison authorities should be encouraged to establish partnership with the Morarji Desai National Institute of Yoga and learn from Delhi's Sanjeevan Project.
- Trained convicts should be employed as yoga trainer in the jails.
- The Ministry of External affairs can reach out to other countries in need of yoga as a tool to reduce recidivism.
- Yoga and meditation should be practiced by the juvenile delinquents in "Children Homes" and by women in "Women Homes".

Conclusion:

Gurudev Sri Sri Ravi Shankar,⁶ founder of "The Art of Living" says "Inside every culprit is a victim crying for help, if you heal the victim, you eliminate crime from planet". When prison inmates practice yoga, meditation and Sudarshan Kriya, a special breathing technique, they experience freedom and become able to forget the past. They develop a positive approach also to the future. In this way prisoners are transformed that means society is transformed.

Bibliography:

- B.K.S. Iyengar, "Yoga the Path to Holistic Health", D.K. Publisher (5 July, 2021)
- Michael D. Huggins & Carol A. Horton, "Best Practices for Yoga in Criminal Justice System" Create Space Independent Pub (24 Nov. 2017), Paperback.

- Pandhy P. (2006), "Crime & Criminology (Vol.1)", Isha Book, Delhi

References :

1. Patanjali Yoga Darshan.
2. "Urban Yogi", founded in March 2020, partly funded by Sport England's Tackling Inequalities Fund.
3. Shaked Kovalsky et al. Int 9. Offender Ther Comp Criminal. 2021 May, "Can Yoga Overcome Criminality? The Impact of Yoga on Recidivism in Israeli Prisons".
4. <http://www.livelaw.in>
5. <http://www.doyou.com>
6. Gurudev Sri Sri Ravi Shankar, "Notes for the Journey Within: Essentials of the Art of Living", Greenleaf Book Group LLC (31 August 2023)

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